

Kunhali Marakkars - Tracing the Naval Defence of Kunhali Marakkars against the Portuguese in the 16th Century Malabar

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ABSTRACT

India was an abode of natural resources, which is also why it attracted foreign colonisers. In 1498, the Portuguese sailor Vasco da Gama set foot on the Malabar Coast, altering Indian history forever. The atrocities unleashed on the civilians and ruthless trade, drew opposition both inland and waters. The Zamorins of Calicut defended the Portuguese on land and his admirals **Kunhali Marakkars** defended them on the Arabian Sea. This paper aims in tracing the history of four Kunhali's Naval defence against the Portuguese in the 16th century and to appreciate their efforts in defending the first European power in India.

KEYWORDS: Kunhali Marakkar, Naval Defence, Portuguese, Malabar, Zamorins, Calicut

Introduction:

India has been the primary target of trade monopoly and colonialism for the time and eternity. India was the land of spices and natural resources that attracted foreign powers such as Portuguese, Dutch, French, and Britain. Many distant countries had trade relations with India in the olden days. The trade with India via land route was extortionate for the foreigners and the capture of Constantinople by Ottoman Turks in 1453 C.E made things complicated. So, the European powers explored a sea route to connect themselves to India for its spices, especially “Pepper”. Among the European nations, Portuguese voyagers had officially found the first sea route to India in 1498 C.E. King Manuel I ordered the voyage to India and appointed Vasco da Gama, a Portuguese sailor and explorer as the head and captain of the fleet. Vasco da Gama started sailing from Lisbon, Portugal on July 8, 1497, with four ships and 170 crew members. He landed on the Malabar Coast, Kappad Beach, Pantalayani (Quilandy), and Calicut (Kozhikode) on May 20, 1498. The Portuguese fleet returned back to Portugal a few months later with almost sixty times the profit of what they brought and with loads of spices mainly pepper and dried ginger. The Portuguese came over and over, for spice, spreading of their religion, and trade monopoly.

Malabar encompasses parts of present-day Northern Kerala and Coastal Karnataka. Malabar previously had commercial ties with Arabia, Rome, and China. Calicut, Cranganore (Kodungallur), and Quilon (Kollam) were their ports on call respectively. The Arabs took over control of the trade via sea and dominated it from the 12th century to the 16th century. During this period, Islam spread all over the Malabar coast. The Arabs traded on land as well, dominating the spice trade with Western Europe. So, Malabar was a hub of cultural fusion, and Kerala is also called the “Spice Garden of India”.

Political Scenario:

When the Portuguese landed on the Malabar Coast, the trade was controlled by the Arab merchants in alliance with the native rulers. Calicut was ruled by the Zamorins/ *Samoothiris*. The Zamorins were the hereditary Nair ruler and the central character in the history of Kerala for about nine hundred and forty years from 826 A.D to 1766 A.D. For about eight centuries the Zamorins were recognized as the *Rakshapurusha* or Protector of the *Mamankam*, the national festival held once in twelve years. Though Zamorin welcomed the Portuguese with hospitality, he was not impressed by the arrival of the foreigners in his land. It also created unrest among the Muslim

merchants who viewed the Portuguese as a threat to their trade. After a trouble-free initial trade link, the relations between the Zamorin and the Portuguese begin to fall apart. Zamorins had a great naval fleet and admirals appointed for them to execute the task of fighting against the Portuguese. These admirals were given the title “Kunhali Marakkar” by the Zamorin and were the head of the naval fleets of Calicut against the Portuguese on the Arabian Seawaters. And thus, Muslim Naval admirals of Zamorins, “Kunhali Marakkars” enters the storyline and started safeguarding the Calicut Coast and their trade from the Portuguese captains. Notably, there were four Kunhali Marakkars who valiantly defended Calicut from the Portuguese. Meanwhile, the Portuguese built ties with Calicut’s grave enemy, Rajah of Cochin, and gave and received help when and wherever necessary.

The Kunhalis/ Kunjalis – Origin:

Kunhali Marakkars was the face of Muslim resistance against the Portuguese during the period from 1507-1600 CE in Malabar. According to the Mappila traditions of Kerala, Marakkars hail from Cochin (Kochi) and were marine merchants. When the Rajah of Cochin joined hands with the Portuguese, the Marakkars found it difficult to go on with their trade, and realising the threat from the foreign powers, they shifted from Cochin and migrated to Ponnani, which is a port belonging to the Zamorin. There is another version of their origin which suggests, that they were descendants of the Arab merchants who settled in Malabar in the 7th century. When the Portuguese Governor Francesco de Almeida attacked Ponnani, the Marakkars shifted their base to Putupattanam. There were four Kunhali Marakkars.

1. Kunhali Marakkar I – Kutty Ali/ Kutty Ahmed Marakkar (1507- 1531) / (1524 – 1538)
2. Kunhali Marakkar II – Son of Kutty Ali Marakkar (1531/1538 – 1569)
3. Kunhali Marakkar III – Pattu/ Paathu Marakkar (1569 – 1595)
4. Kunhali Marakkar IV – Muhammad Ali Marakkar (1595 – 1605)

Kunhali Marakkars (I, II, III & IV) led the naval defence of the Calicut Zamorins on the Arabian Sea in the 16th century. Their personal life is less known.

Kunhali Marakkars, the Portuguese, and the Arabian Sea:

Kunhali Marakkar I was a valiant leader and his sea warfare strategies helped Calicut fight the Portuguese to a greater extent. In the words of A. Sreedhara Menon, “He had been to the Zamorin in his fight with the Portuguese what Drake had been to the Elizabeth of England in her fight with the Spaniards”. After the destruction of Ponnani by the Portuguese Viceroy Francesco de Almeida in 1507, the Kunhali Marakkars, admirals of the Zamorin's fleet, shifted their headquarters to Kottakkal. Kunhali Marakkar I adopted guerilla warfare tactics that avoided bloodbaths and gore. Their navy comprises many swift light vessels that carry only thirty to forty men. These vessels moved quickly, inflicted damage to enemy fleets, and would be back to safety effortlessly. The agitated Portuguese witnessed their existing naval supremacy begin to tremble. However, the Portuguese managed to secure occasional victories. In 1513, the Portuguese on their way to Gujarat, captured some of the vessels of the Zamorin and also prisoned a few Kunhali's men including Ali Ibrahim Marakkar and Kutti Ibrahim. Making use of the opportunity, the Portuguese obtained consent to build a fort at Chaliyam. Despite Kunhali being against it, the construction of the fort was completed within twenty-six days and it later served as a base for the Portuguese to attack the Zamorin in-land. Soon, the relationship between Zamorin and the Portuguese thawed, because the latter failed to share their collected customs revenue from the Chaliyam Port. Kutty Ali, inculcated fear in the hearts of the Portuguese in Malabar. Under Kutty Ali, in 1524, a large and effective fleet took to the sea and did great damage to Portuguese trade. The Portuguese Governor Lope Vaz de Sampayo came into action against Kutty Ali of Cannanore but the results were not decisive. Kutty Ali's gallantry on the sea was such as to strike terror into the hearts of the Portuguese, and for over two years he virtually cut off all connection between Cochin and Goa. Finally, the Governor made an intensive effort to destroy his power, and in a fight in 1528, Kutty Ali was taken captive. This however did not affect the growth of Zamorin's sea power; for Kunhali II, the son of Kutty Ali was soon to follow in his father's footsteps with greater success.

Kutti Ahmed Marakkar, the leading commander on the Calicut side, was killed in 1531. Kunhali Marakkar II took his place. Even the Portuguese writers were kindled with admiration by his potential and knightly skills. In a particular year, he seized over fifty ships and he put to the sword the entire crew. As a result, the war in the Malabar waters escalated, and both the Portuguese and the Indians suffered huge losses. Kunhali started charging against the Portuguese's possessions in Ceylon and East Coast. For almost seven years, Kunhali's supremacy at sea caused heavy losses to

the Portuguese. In 1533, Kunhali II surrounded Cape Comorin and attacked the Portuguese settlement at Nagapattinam on the East Coast. Using the moment, the Zamorin attacked the Portuguese territories in Kerala and captured Cranganore (Kodungallur). When Zamorin moved towards Cochin, Kunhali's fleet reached Cochin waters to divert the Portuguese naval fleet. But there they were overhauled by a Portuguese squadron and the fight went against the Calicut forces. Kunhali himself had to escape in disguise to Calicut. The Portuguese managed to defeat them on both land and on water. In 1537, however, a new Calicut fleet appeared on the sea, which managed a very successful campaign against Portuguese merchant vessels. The Portuguese Governor Martim de Sousa tried to chase the vessels, but the Marakkars evaded him and continued their valorous career on the sea inflicting serious loss on the trade as well as the naval honour of the enemy. It was only on the 20th of February 1538, that Martim de Sousa was able to fight a great battle with the Marakkars and to get the sea cleared for a short time. The success was just in time because the Portuguese had soon to organise their whole strength to meet the Turkish expedition under Suleiman Pasha Al Khadim. It was early in 1537, that Suleiman Pasha, the Turkish Governor of Egypt, began the preparations for an attack on Portuguese power in the Indian seas. The much-anticipated Egyptian fleet under the Turkish in 1538 turned out to be helpless. The withdrawal of the Turks came as a great blow to the Zamorin. Fifteen years of never-ending struggle had exhausted his treasury. Four of the Zamorin's fleets had been sunk, and the trade of Calicut was flagging. The Portuguese had established themselves at Chaliyam, giving them a distinctive position to carry on the war against Zamorin. In 1540, the Zamorin negotiated for peace with the Portuguese. The Portuguese and Zamorin signed the "Treaty of Ponnani" on January 1, 1540. Portuguese as the dominant gained the virtual trade monopoly of pepper and ginger in Calicut and was also assured non-intervention by the Zamorin in the wars of Portuguese with other native powers. The Treaty of Ponnani dwindled in 1550 and fresh clashes resulted in nothing but the draining of resources by both parties. Peace was reinstated in 1555. During this period, the Portuguese unleashed atrocities in their acquired territories in Kerala. They destroyed Mosques, and houses, and massacred civilians unjustly.

Kunhali Marakkar III (Pattu Marakkar) took over the naval defence of Calicut against the Portuguese in 1569. Kunhali III had several brave men as his lieutenants, Captain Kutti Pokkar being important among them. He employed foreign experts to design new ships after the European model and to give training to his men in cutting-edge sea warfare. Kunhali III believed in self-sustenance and also convinced the Zamorin of the policy of it because relying on outsiders like Egyptians was only expensive and didn't yield the expected fruit. All the arms, ammunition, and vessels were built in

Calicut. Kunhali Also set up observation posts at elevated sites all along the coast to observe and report the Portuguese movements. The native vessels were free from the disturbances of the Portuguese. In 1571, the Zamorin launched an attack on the Portuguese at Chaliyam and besieged the Portuguese fort for days together. The siege was so effective that the Portuguese provisions ran short and they suffered a lot. The Zamorin's fleet under Kunhali III cut off supplies to the Portuguese garrison from Cochin and Cannanore. At last, Chaliyam fell into the hands of Zamorin and it stopped the Portuguese on the Malabar Coast. In appreciation for the services of Kunhali Marakkar III, Zamorin permitted him to erect a fort and a shipyard at Putupattanam, the headquarters of the Marakkar at the mouth of Agalapuzha. A fort at Kottakkal was erected (1572- 1573). The Zamorin also granted privileges and powers to Kunhali, which his highest-ranking Nair chieftains enjoyed. The Nairs were more of a community than a caste. The Rajahs and Chieftains depended on the Nair militia who thus enjoyed nearly a monopoly of political influence in the Malabar. Kunhali III instilled terror in Portuguese, for he and his men acquired supremacy over the Indian Ocean from the Persian Gulf to Ceylon and often involved Portuguese in decisive fights which resulted in severe damages and more casualties. Trade almost came to a standstill for the Portuguese on the Malabar Coast and they decided to adopt the policy of conciliation with the Zamorin, for they realized that it is the only way that they can crush the power of the Kunhali Marakkar.

Kunhali Marakkar III passed away and his nephew Muhammad Ali Kunhali Marakkar succeeded him as Kunhali Marakkar IV in 1595. His relations with the Zamorin were not good and he also begrudged the permission given to the Portuguese to build a factory in Ponnani by the Zamorin. Kunhali IV tried showing his resentment by strengthening his fort by digging trenches and building towers armed with cannons. These acts infuriated the Zamorin. In fact, Kunhali started to directly distance himself from the Zamorin and tried to be independent. The relationship between Kunhali and Zamorin deviated and the Portuguese made diplomatic ideas to isolate Kunhali. In 1597, an agreement was vovod between the Zamorin and the Portuguese, in which they would attack the Kunhali's fortress. Zamorin by land and Portuguese by sea. The Kottakkal fort was blockaded by the Zamorin's forces under a Portuguese contingent in 1599. It was not successful because the Portuguese failed to blockade the fort by sea. Kunhali IV was elated by his success. The Portuguese again made a similar agreement with the Zamorin to attack the Marakkars fort. It was decided to equally share the spoils of war and if Kunhali was to be captured alive, he was to be kept under the custody of the Portuguese. The town and fortress of Kottakkal were to be taken by the Zamorin. An army comprising 6000 men started the besiege on the Kottakkal fort in 1600. The sea blockade was

under the Portuguese captain Andre Furtado. Realising his situation, Kunhali Marakkar IV surrender himself to the Zamorin, on the promise of general pardon. The Zamorin handed him over to the Portuguese based on their earlier agreement. They took him and his men to Goa. Not ready for a pardon, the Portuguese executed all of them cold-blooded. Kunhali IV's body was cut into four pieces and displayed in four different places. His head was salted and was sent to Cannanore and displayed there on a stand to threaten the native chiefs and the Muslims in the marketplace. His tragic end and heroic acts earned him the halo of martyrdom. The Portuguese were victorious in putting an end to the Marakkar hegemony in Malabar but their supremacy was not restored for now a new adversary had entered the scenario. A Dutch fleet of four vessels was sent to India in 1595 and by 1599 they were dominating the Eastern trade. Though the Portuguese's nominal authority went on in Malabar for half a century, their political paramountcy vanished. Their spice trade was no longer profitable and a century-long upper hand in the trade monopoly by the Portuguese ended abruptly in India. Though their efforts failed miserably, Kunhali Marakkars was the foe of the Portuguese authorities in India for almost a century.

Marakkar Smarakam:

The house belonging to the descendants of Kunhali Marakkar at Payyoli village was destroyed by the Portuguese in the later part of the 16th century. The aged one-storeyed house was later refurbished to the present style and declared by the Kerala state department of Archaeology as a protected monument in 1976. A building was constructed on the side of the old one in conventional style as a library and Museum using the MP fund of the former Rajya Sabha MP Abdul Samad Samadani. The museum introduces the history of Kunhali Marakkars and also exhibits specimens collected from the premises such as stone cannonballs unearthed from the sites of the fort of Kunhali in Kottakkal. Swords and a model of the fort of Kunhali Marakkar are also exhibited. The Smarakam is located in Payyoli village, Quilandy taluk, Kozhikode district.

Conclusion:

Kunhali Marakkars were the face of resistance in the 16th century Indian waters against the first European power to set foot in India since Alexander. Kunhalis naval warfare strategies and their skills in guerrilla warfare in Sea are commendable. More research should be done and works written on the life of Marakkars, for it can inspire thousands against the modern forms of tyranny. Many heroic and scholastic personalities are being neglected in Indian History for they belonged to the

Muslim and Minority Communities. Even though some historic works are written on the Admirals, they are limited. Their bravery is still alive in the folk songs of Kerala, which glorify the achievements of Kunhali Marakkars. Movies have also been made about Kunhali Marakkars' life and adventures. The Kunhali Marakkars was first seen on-screen in the Malayalam film, “Kunhali Marakkars” in 1967 directed by S S Rajan. This movie won the best feature film in Malayalam. Again, Kunhali was seen on the big screen in the film, “Marakkar: Lion of the Arabian Sea” directed by Priyadarshan in 2021. Although Kunhalis were not successful in the end, it is proud to know that our ancestors didn't stay idle. In the words of K. M. Panikkar, “There can be no doubt, that the lives of these chiefs reflect glory and honour on all Malabar, for their achievements against the naval tyranny of the Portuguese form indeed a great chapter in the history of Malabar”.

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